

Single Nucleotide Polymorphism (SNPs) Of TCF7L2 Gene with Susceptibility to Type 2 Diabetes in Vokkaliga Community of Mysuru

Lakshmi Nivedya Sree*¹, Deepthi Gowda²

¹Sapthagiri Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Center, Bangalore, India. 560090

²Maurya Institute of Allied Health sciences, Mysuru, India. 570009

ABSTRACT

Background: Transcription factor 7-like 2 (TCF7L2) variants have been associated with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus in multiple ethnic groups. Specifically associated variants increase the risk of T2DM 1.5-fold in a heterozygote and 2.4-fold in homozygote, corresponding to a population attributable risk of 21%. This makes TCF7L2 variants the strongest known genetic risk factors for T2DM. The present study aimed to identify for the first time the single nucleotide polymorphism in the TCF7L2 gene in T2DM subjects between the age group of 40-55 years in the Vokkaliga community of Mysuru, Karnataka and also to investigate the potential association of this polymorphism with glucose metabolism and HbA1c levels. The study also aimed at comparing the physical parameters such as Body Mass Index (BMI), height, weight etc. in diabetic and non-diabetic groups. **Materials and methods:** The study included a total of 130 subjects in which 71 were diabetic and 59 were non-diabetics aged between 40-55 years of Vokkaliga community of Mysuru. Their BMI was calculated based on their height, weight, and waist to hip ratio. The venous blood samples were collected and the random blood sugar (RBS) and glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) was estimated. DNA was extracted from blood and genotyped by Polymerase Chain Reaction- Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism (PCR-RFLP) with specific primers to amplify the fragment for digestion with a restriction enzyme (RsaI). Statistical analysis was done by the Multifactor Dimensionality Reduction (MDR) method and the physical parameters were compared. **Results:** RBS and HbA1c showed a statistically significant difference between the diabetic and non-diabetic groups ($p = <0.001$, $p = <0.0018$) respectively. An amplification product of 201bp was obtained which was further used for detecting the polymorphism by the RFLP method. However, the polymorphism was not detected in T2DM patients belonging to this community. **Conclusions:** The results showed no significant correlation between the TCF7L2 gene polymorphism and T2DM in the Vokkaliga community of Mysuru. The lack of association might have come from the small sample size. Further studies relating TCF7L2 gene polymorphism and T2DM with larger sample size must be explored in order to confirm the observed finding.

Keywords: TCF7L2, T2DM, Vokkaliga community, HbA1c, PCR-RFLP, Multifactor Dimensionality Reduction method

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes was one of the first diseases described which meant "too big urine emptying." The first cases described are believed to be of type 1 diabetes. Indian doctors recognized the disease at about the same time and named it as madhumeha or "honey urine," nothing but the urine will attract ants. Diabetes mellitus is a globally highly prevalent chronic disease. This happens when the insulin released by the pancreas is not enough or when the body cannot use the insulin produced effectively¹. Prevention and treatment

involve keeping a healthy diet, regular physical exercise, normal body weight and avoiding tobacco use. In people with the disease it is important to control blood pressure and to maintain proper foot care. Insulin injections shall be used to treat T1DM. T2DM may be treated with insulin-free or with medication. Approximately 366 million people were diagnosed with DM worldwide in 2011 and this is expected to increase to 552 million by 2030 as per the WHO². DM is categorized according to the pathogenic mechanism leading to hyperglycemia, as opposed to earlier parameters such as age of onset or

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

form of therapy. Type 1 and Type 2 are classified as two broad categories of DM. As pathogenic processes proceed, both forms of diabetes are followed by a period of irregular homeostasis of glucose. Type 1 DM is the product of insulin deficiency in its entirety or near totality. Type 2 DM is a heterogeneous group of disorders with varying degrees of insulin resistance, impaired insulin secretion and increased production of glucose³. As per the study conducted by Anthropological Survey of India, Southern Regional Centre, Mysuru, it shows that the Gangadikara Vokkaligas community of Karnataka is having high prevalence to T2D. Gangadikara Vokkaliga also referred to as Gowda, is a community with its origin in India. They are landlords, village headmen and known to be dominant and powerful caste which is also a major dominant agricultural community⁴. Gangadikara Vokkaliga of Mysore has a very high prevalence of diabetes (27.5 %) compared to coastal Karnataka population (16 percent) and Chennai population (15.5 percent). All male and female diabetes are found to have more body weight compared to non-diabetes, although they are subject to restrictions on medicine and diet. However, compared to male diabetes, female diabetes is obese⁵. Single Nucleotide Polymorphism (SNP) is a variation in a single nucleotide that occurs at a specific position in the genome, where each variation is present in some appreciable degree within a population. SNPs of the following genes are commonly associated with type 2 diabetes. Transcription factors 7 like 2 also known as TCF7L2 or TCF4 is a protein acting as a transcription factor in humans which is encoded by the TCF7L2 gene⁶. The TCF7L2 gene is located on the chromosome 10q25.2-q25.3 which contains 19 exons, and has autosomal dominant inheritance^{7,8}. KCNJ11 is a protein coding gene. Kir6.2 is a major subunit of the ATP-sensitive K⁺ channel, and inward-rectifier potassium ion channel. The gene encoding the channel is called KCNJ11 and mutations in this gene are associated with congenital hyperinsulinism⁹. Adiponectin also referred to as GBP-28, apM1, AdipoQ and Acrp30 is a protein hormone which is involved in regulating glucose levels as well as fatty acid breakdown. In humans, it is encoded by the ADIPOQ gene and it is produced in the Adipose tissue¹⁰. DM in India probably approaches epidemic proportions. Worryingly, it is now known that diabetes is associated with a number

of complications and happens within the nation at a comparatively younger age. The incidence of diabetes is expected to double globally from 171 million in 2000 to 366 million in 2030 with a highest rise in India, according to Wild et al^{11,12}. The SNPs of genes such as TCF7L2, KCNJ11 and ADIPONECTIN which are susceptible to type 2 diabetes is carried out in the Gangadikara Vokkaliga community of Mysuru district. The main aim of the study is to assess the single nucleotide polymorphism of TCF7L2 gene is carried out which is susceptible to type 2 diabetes in Gangadikara Vokkaliga community of Mysuru district. The biochemical parameters will be correlated with the identified SNPs in the study population.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Study Design and Population

A community-based case-control study was conducted over a period of 18 months (August 2018 to February 2020) to investigate the association of TCF7L2 gene polymorphism with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) in the Vokkaliga community of Mysuru, Karnataka. Participants were recruited from community-dominated regions such as K.G. Koppal and Bannur. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee, and informed written consent was collected from all participants.

Sample Size and Selection Criteria

Based on an expected diabetes prevalence of 27.5% in the target population, a confidence level of 95%, absolute precision of 10%, and power of 80%, the estimated sample size was calculated to be 80 in each group. Ultimately, a total of 130 participants were recruited, including 71 confirmed T2DM patients (cases) and 59 non-diabetic individuals (controls) aged 40–55 years.

- **Inclusion Criteria:**

- Cases: Diagnosed T2DM patients with random blood sugar (RBS) >150 mg/dL.
- Controls: Non-diabetic individuals with RBS <150 mg/dL.

- **Exclusion Criteria:**

- Individuals with Type 1 diabetes, other systemic illnesses, or outside the age range.
- Pregnant or lactating women and individuals from other communities.

Clinical and Anthropometric Data Collection

Participant data were collected using a pre-tested and validated questionnaire covering:

- Demographics
- Medical and family history
- Lifestyle and dietary habits
- Anthropometric measurements including height, weight, waist and hip circumference, and blood pressure
- Body Mass Index (BMI) was calculated using the formula:
$$\text{BMI} = \text{Weight (kg)} / \text{Height}^2 (\text{m}^2)$$

Sample Collection and Processing

Venous blood samples (4 ml) were collected under aseptic conditions:

- 2 ml in plain vacutainer for biochemical analysis
- 2 ml in EDTA vacutainer for DNA extraction

Samples were transported in portable cold boxes to the laboratory within 30 minutes. Serum was separated by centrifugation at 6000 rpm for 10 minutes.

Biochemical Analysis

- Random Blood Sugar (RBS) was measured using the GOD-POD enzymatic method.
- Glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) levels were estimated using the HPLC method.

DNA Extraction and Quantification

Genomic DNA was extracted from whole blood using the salting-out method (TKM buffer). Purity and concentration were assessed using a Nanodrop spectrophotometer (DeNovix) by measuring absorbance ratios at A260/280 and A260/230. DNA integrity was confirmed via 1.5% agarose gel electrophoresis.

Primer Design and Validation

Specific primers targeting the TCF7L2 gene were designed and validated using NCBI Primer-BLAST and bioinformatics tools for specificity, melting temperature (T_m), and ΔG values. The expected PCR product size was 201 bp.

Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)

PCR amplification was optimised using gradient PCR. The reaction mix included:

- DNA template (~100 ng)
- Forward and reverse primers (10 μM)
- dNTPs, Taq DNA polymerase, buffer, and MgCl_2

Thermal cycling conditions:

- Initial denaturation: 94°C for 5 min
- 35 cycles of: 94°C for 30 sec, annealing at optimised T_m (56–60°C) for 30 sec, 72°C for 45 sec
- Final extension: 72°C for 7 min

Amplified products were visualised using gel electrophoresis with ethidium bromide staining.

Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism (RFLP)

Amplified TCF7L2 gene fragments were digested with the *RsaI* restriction enzyme under optimal conditions. Restriction products were analysed by agarose gel electrophoresis to detect polymorphic patterns.

- Positive controls (Lambda DNA) and No Template Controls (NTC) were included in each batch.
- DNA fragment sizes were compared against a 100 bp molecular marker.

High Resolution Melt (HRM) Analysis

Samples with ambiguous or unexpected banding patterns in RFLP were subjected to HRM analysis using real-time PCR. Amplification and melting curve profiles were used to identify sequence variations.

Sanger Sequencing

Selected samples (suspected positive cases and matched controls) were subjected to Sanger sequencing for confirmation of SNPs.

Chromatograms were aligned with the reference TCF7L2 sequence using BLAST for mutation identification.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using Multifactor Dimensionality Reduction (MDR) and standard descriptive and inferential techniques. Group comparisons (e.g. HbA1c, BMI) were evaluated using Student's t-test or Mann-Whitney U test, where appropriate. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 130 participants were included in the study, comprising 71 individuals with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) and 59 age- and gender-matched non-diabetic controls from the Vokkaliga community of Mysuru. The mean age of participants was comparable across groups. Significant differences were observed in random blood sugar (RBS) and HbA1c levels between the diabetic and control groups ($p < 0.001$ and $p = 0.0018$, respectively). Body mass index (BMI) was higher in diabetic subjects, though not statistically significant (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic variables for Cases and Control.

Demographic variables	Cases (N=71)(%)	Controls (N=59)(%)	P value
Sex			
Male	41 (58.6)	29 (41.4)	0.328*
Female	30 (50)	30 (50)	
Age			
<45	16 (40.0)	24 (60.0)	0.026*
>45	55 (61.1)	35 (38.9)	
Family history			
Yes	30 (56)	23 (44)	0.523 **
No	41 (53.2)	36 (46.8)	
Diet			
Yes	57 (55.3)	46 (44.7)	0.891*
No	14 (53.8)	12 (46.2)	
Smoking			
Yes	13 (56.5)	10 (43.5)	0.840*
No	58 (54.2)	49 (45.8)	
Alcohol			
Yes	13 (59.1)	9 (40.9)	0.644*
No	58 (53.7)	50 (46.3)	
BMI			
<25	33 (55)	27 (45)	0.935*
>25	38 (54.3)	32 (45.7)	

Genomic DNA extracted from all samples showed good purity and concentration as illustrates in Figure 1 and Table 2.

Figure 1: Blood Genomic DNA separated under 1.5% Agarose Gel Electrophoresis, and Image

captured using Gel documentation unit (SYNGENE). A representative image for 1st 10 cases and control samples.

Table 2: DNA quantification purity assessment values by Nanodrop.

S.No.	Sample No.	Ab 260nm	Ab 260/230	Ab 260/280	DNA conc. (ng/μl)
1	D1	7.34	2.37	1.9	367.088
2	D2	7.08	2.44	1.87	354.267
3	D3	2.63	2.56	1.89	131.944
4	D4	8.96	2.35	1.91	448.336
5	D5	3.82	2.46	1.92	191.296
6	D6	1.32	6.82	1.75	66.205
7	D7	7.48	2.4	1.88	374.294
8	D8	5.92	2.34	1.88	296.206
9	D9	4.33	2.33	1.92	216.624
10	D10	7.41	2.42	1.87	370.67
11	C1	6.35	2.41	1.89	317.786
12	C2	3.43	2.25	1.86	171.792
13	C3	2.91	2.56	1.88	145.759
14	C4	10.27	2.38	1.88	513.506
15	C5	11.33	2.38	1.88	566.859
16	C6	48.99	2.33	1.87	2449.973
17	C7	9.44	2.38	1.89	472.285
18	C8	7.81	2.35	1.87	390.748
19	C9	7.51	2.33	1.88	375.792
20	C10	4.05	1.62	1.81	202.889

The TCF7L2 gene primer validation was done using several bioinformatics tools and was found to be acceptable as depicted in Table 3 and Figure 2.

Detailed primer reports						
Primer pair 1						
	Sequence (5'→3')	Length	Tm	GC%	Self complementarity	Self 3' complementarity
Forward primer	TTAGAGAGCTAAGCACTTTTATAGTA	26	57.87	34.62	7.00	3.00
Reverse primer	AGAGATGAAATGTAGCAGTGAAGTG	25	59.13	40.00	3.00	2.00
Products on target templates						
> NC_000010.11 Homo sapiens chromosome 10, GRCh38.p13 Primary Assembly						
product length = 201						
Features associated with this product:						
transcription factor 7-like 2 isoform 4						
transcription factor 7-like 2 isoform 7						
Forward primer	1 TTAGAGAGCTAAGCACTTTTATAGTA	26				
Template	112998564	A..	112998589			
Reverse primer	1 AGAGATGAAATGTAGCAGTGAAGTG	25				
Template	112998764		112998740			

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Figure 2: Primer for TCF7L2 gene utilized in the study showed its specificity towards target sequence as validated by using NCBI primer designing tool/Primer Blast.

Table 3: TCF7L2 Primer details.

S.No	Primer name	Sequence 5'-3'	Tm	GC %	Primer dimer DG	Restriction site	Product size	Digested product size
1	TCF7L 2-F	TTAGAGAGCTAAGCAC TTTTTAG	57.8	34.6	-4.32	5'...GTAC...3' 3'...CATG...5'	201 bp	176 bp & 25 bp
2	TCF7L 2-R	AGAGATGAAATGTAGC AGTGAAGTG	59.1	40.0				

Figure 3 showing Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) successfully amplified a 201 bp fragment of the TCF7L2 gene in all samples.

Figure 3: Detection of Human-TCF7L2 gene using PCR at optimized PCR condition yielded specific product with size of 201bp. The above representative image is of TCF7L2 gene product derived from Cases (D1-D9) and control (C1-C9) which are specific in size as expected. Similarly, all samples from cases and controls yielded specific product

which validated all samples for the presence of TCF7L2 gene. 50bp marker was loaded along with samples in each gel to mark the size of PCR product. Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism (RFLP) analysis using RsaI enzyme predominantly showed undigested products in both groups, indicating the absence of polymorphism at the targeted site as depicted in Figure 4

Figure 4: Detection of Human-TCF7L2 gene polymorphism using RFLP at optimized restriction digestion condition yielded mainly undigested product (wild type) with specific product size of 201bp, similar with that of PCR product. Some of the samples from Cases group (Diabetics) as mentioned above yielded spurious fragment corresponding to the size of one of the DNA fragment of TCF7L2 i.e. 176bp. These samples were further screened through HRM to find if these samples possess different T_m value or melting temperature. Positive control PC and No Template Control NTC yielded expected result as depicted in the gel image. 100bp marker was loaded

along with samples in each gel to mark the size of digested product. A few diabetic samples displayed atypical banding patterns suggestive of possible sequence variation, which were further analysed using High Resolution Melt (HRM) (Figure 5) and Sanger sequencing (Figure 6). However, HRM analysis revealed no significant difference in melting temperature profiles between cases and controls, (Table 4) and Sanger sequencing confirmed the absence of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in the amplified region. Overall, no TCF7L2 gene polymorphism was detected among the T2DM cases studied.

Figure 5: DNA samples with spurious fragment after RFLP for TCF7L2 gene were subjected for HRM along with Beta Actin as an internal control. Melting peaks (Left side) apparently at the same position of

melting temperature are of TCF7L2 gene from both suspected cases and respective controls. Melting peaks (Right side) belong to Beta actin-an internal control. NTC didn't show any amplification as expected and hence no melting peak was generated.

Table 4: HRM result of suspected cases and controls.

Age group (Years)	Suspected Cases		Controls		Control T_m range (°C)
	Sample No.	Melt T_m	Sample No.	Melt T_m	
45-50 Male	D60	81.6	C31	81.8	81.7-81.8
50-55 Male	D54	81.7	C49	81.8	
	D56	81.7			
	D62	81.7			
50-55 Female	D41	81.8	C7	81.7	
	D58	81.7			

Figure 6: Sanger's sequence chromatogram of Case D60-Forward reaction.

DISCUSSION

Transcription factor 7-like 2 (TCF7L2) variants have been associated with T2DM in multiple ethnic groups. Specific associated variants increase the risk of T2DM 1.5-fold in heterozygote and 2.4-fold in homozygote, corresponding to a population attributable risk of 21%. This makes TCF7L2 variants the strongest known genetic risk factors for T2DM^{13, 14}. The major findings of the present study were that the polymorphism of TCF7L2 gene is not associated with T2DM in the Vokkaliga community in Mysuru district, Karnataka, India. Subjects ranged from ages 40 to 55 (71 Diabetic and 59 Non-Diabetic). Ten of the 130 subjects were newly diagnosed with diabetes, and two of them had a family history of diabetes. There were no major variations in demographic characteristics between Diabetic and Non-Diabetic groups. Table 18 discusses demographic features of the two groups. It was observed that the percentage of males (58 percent) in Diabetic was high compared to the percentage of females (50 percent), but the percentage of females in Non-diabetic (50 percent) was comparatively higher than that of males (41 percent). There was no statistically significant difference between the groups ($P=0.328$). The amount of Glucose was found to have a statistically significant difference between diabetic and non-diabetic subjects ($P < 0.001$). HbA1C is a statistically significant

difference ($P < 0.0018$) between subjects. BMI does not differ significantly between subjects ($P = 0.559$). DNA from 130 blood samples was obtained and the polymorphism in this gene was detected along with β -actin as an internal control (250bp). The primers for this study were selected based on preselected articles^{17,18}. Primer length is 201bp; this was followed by qPCR, RFLP, and sequencing, and the result observed was negative for the TCF7L2 gene polymorphism in this community. Previous paper studies about the prevalence of type 2 diabetes and obesity among Mysuru's Gangadikara Vokkaliga⁵ are compared to the present paper on this community. However, males are higher in diabetes than females in this community. It is observed that, although they are under specific diet with medication, there is no significant difference between diabetic and non-diabetic. Several studies exploring the relationship between the TCF7L2 gene polymorphism and T2DM reportedly proposed the TCF7L2 gene polymorphism as a strong candidate in the development of T2DM^{13,14}. Similarly, Dalia et al. conducted an analysis including 400 subjects, out of which 180 were cases and 220 were controls, and concluded that the TCF7L2 gene polymorphism was positively associated with T2DM¹⁵. Another study conducted by Mojgan Allahdini et al. demonstrates the presence of the rs7903146 polymorphism in the Iranian population, suggesting susceptibility to T2DM¹⁶. However, a study conducted by Mohammad Pourahmadi et al. suggested that there was no significant association between the TCF7L2 gene

polymorphism with T2DM in individuals of Jahrom City, Iran¹⁶. Several limitations of this study should be considered. Mainly, there was a relatively small sample size in the study. We included only subjects between the age group of 40 and 55 of the Vokkaliga community of Mysuru. Further studies with larger sample size should be conducted in the future.

CONCLUSION

The current study is considered to be the first to detect the polymorphism in TCF7L2 gene in type 2 diabetes patients of Vokkaliga Community in Mysuru district which will help draw a baseline for further diabetes research studies in Mysuru, Karnataka, India. The study aimed to detect the polymorphism in above mentioned genes of T2DM patients. The potential association between this polymorphism with biochemical parameters such as BMI, glucose and HbA1C were also evaluated. Our findings showed no significant correlation between the TCF7L2 gene polymorphism and T2DM in Mysuru population. Consequently, we were unable to find the SNPs in the TCF7L2 gene. The samples showed expected amplification of beta-actin with product size of 250bp. All in all, the lack of association might have come from the small sample size. To ensure enhanced future treatments and preventive measures, further studies relating TCF7L2 gene polymorphism and T2DM with larger sample size must be explored in order to confirm the observed findings.

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HOW TO CITE: Lakshmi Nivedya Sree*, Deepthi Gowda, Single Nucleotide Polymorphism (SNPs) Of TCF7L2 Gene with Susceptibility to Type 2 Diabetes in Vokkaliga Community of Mysuru, *Int. J. Sci. R. Tech.*, 2025, 2 (7), 374-383. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16357792>